

D1.2: First Report

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ABSTRACT:	This report summarizes activities undertaken to realize the stakeholder engagement plan previously presented in deliverable 1.1. It identifies challenges and opportunities that have presented themselves in the project months 4-18 that followed the establishment of the plan.
Keyword List:	

Consortium:

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This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission

1 Review of Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Horizontal Coordination

Main Objectives:

- **Engage** European XR companies and other stakeholders to promote the uptake of the XR Code of Conduct, the Guidance for Interoperability, and the empowerment of end-users;
- **Engage** European XR stakeholders through a digital European forum towards the co-creation and uptake of XR4Human guidance and tools.

Specific Objectives:

- **Define** methodology and develop framework for stakeholder engagement;
- **Build** and manage a digital collaborative platform to facilitate stakeholder dialogue;
- **Guarantee** that XR4Human project's outputs are embedded in broader European considerations and aligned with related Horizon Europe projects and international initiatives;
- **Establish** "The XR4Human European Forum" as a permanent platform.

Deliverable 1.1 defined the stakeholder engagement methodology and plan that would guide activities in WP1 and for tasks 3.1, 3.4, 4.2, 5.2, 5.3, 6.1, 6.4, and 7.2, all of which included engagement with stakeholders. Through a systematic methodology, the report addressed stakeholder identification and engagement, introduced a 7-step model tailored for XR4HUMAN on the basis of an extensive review of similar models, and offered a concrete roadmap for stakeholder engagement activities. It emphasized the importance of transparency, accountability, and the integration of local knowledge in project design. The report concluded with a summary of outcomes and a SWOT analysis, underscoring the significance of ethical stakeholder engagement in achieving sustainable XR development.

1.1 7-Step Plan

1. **Monitor:** Identify and track stakeholder groups, determining their positions, key concerns, level of exposure to the project, and involvement status. Implementation includes the project groundwork phase and consultations with relevant entities.
2. **Message:** Establish communication with stakeholders through various channels like the website, social media, and e-newsletters, considering their specific requirements and preferences.
3. **Create Value:** Unite stakeholders under the central goal of the XR4HUMAN project, addressing each group's special needs and interests. Implementation involves activities such as scientific publications, workshops, conferences, and lab visits.
4. **Involve:** Ensure the involvement and participation of stakeholders at different levels to foster understanding, overcome miscommunications, and establish sustainable connections. Activities include workshops, social media engagement, public events, and forums.
5. **Collaborate:** Generate excitement, acknowledgement, and familiarity with XR technologies among stakeholders, fostering adoption and ethical standards. Activities include workshops, social media engagement, conferences, public events, and forums.
6. **Empower:** Entrust decision-making to key stakeholders, ensuring ethical safety and inclusiveness for all, including the most vulnerable. Activities include website communication, social media engagement, conferences, press releases, and forums.
7. **Innovate:** Collaboratively work on common project objectives, fostering co-creation and co-implementation of new ideas to maintain long-term engagement and participation. Activities include workshops, social media engagement, scientific conferences, website updates, and lab visits.

1.2 Stakeholder Database & Analysis

Deliverable 1.1 defined the stakeholder personas relevant to the XR4HUMAN project as:

1. **Policymakers:** They need to stay informed about how XR technologies impact society and regulate the sector to protect citizens and ensure a fair market.
2. **Non-profit organizations:** These groups are impacted by XR4HUMAN's work and may inform their communities, share findings, or have teams dedicated to digitalization.
3. **Companies:** All types of businesses are affected by XR4HUMAN's work, seeking information on how to leverage XR technologies for profit and adapt to ethical guidelines.
4. **General Public:** Final users of XR technologies, including families and parents concerned about potential harms and risks to children's exposure.

1.3 Engagement Timeline

The defined stakeholder engagement plan includes the following project tasks taking place throughout the duration of the XR4HUMAN project:

1. **WP1:**
 - Task 1.2: Establish and manage the XR4Human European Forum (M4–M36)
 - Task 1.3: Coordinate with European and international initiatives (M7–M36)
 - Task 1.4: Organize XR4Human Encounters (M7–M30) and which refer to workshops, ideation sessions, and conferences.
 - Task 1.5: Ensure project legacy (M30–M36) including sustainability planning and maintenance of the project website and social media channels.
2. **WP2:**
 - Task 2.2: Identify various forms of risks and harm relevant to XR use (M1–M12)
3. **WP3:**
 - Task 3.1: Policy debate analysis (M1–M6): Consultation with policy makers through the Forum, focusing on Step 2 of the stakeholder engagement plan - Message.
 - Task 3.4: Governance debate forum (M13–M36): Continued consultation via the Forum and workshops, involving policymakers and non-profit organizations. This aligns with Step 3 - Create Value.
4. **WP4:**
 - Task 4.2: Co-create the project's Interoperability Guideline (M10–M24): Consultation through the Forum and workshops, involving all stakeholder personas to create value. This aligns with Step 4 - Involve.
5. **WP5:**
 - Task 5.2: Stakeholder consultations (M16–M24): Engagement through the Forum and workshops, focusing on Step 5 - Collaborate.
 - Task 5.3: Creation of the XR Code of Conduct (M22–36): Consultation via the Forum and workshops, involving all personas to collaborate (Step 6: Empower).
6. **WP6:**
 - Task 6.1: Definition, identification and selection of case studies (M1–M12): Empowerment of non-profit organizations through workshops, aligning with Step 6: Empower.
 - Task 6.4: Evaluation of example use cases (M20–M36): Collaboration with all personas through participant recruitment and evaluation, continuing Step 6: Empower.

7. WP7:

- Task 7.2: Elicitation of needs, requirements, and experiences from stakeholders (M7-M18): Consultation through workshops, surveys, and Forum discussions, focusing on Step 7 - Innovate.

2 Execution of Stakeholder Engagement Plan

Deliverable 1.1 presented the stakeholder engagement methodology and plan that would guide engagement activities. It identified the XR4HUMAN website, the Forum, Working Groups, Conferences and Events as the channels by which to execute the strategy.

2.1 Website

Plan: The project's website will be the central mechanism for achieving the Message step of the stakeholder engagement methodology. As mentioned above, stakeholders will find information on the XR4HUMAN project, get information about consortium activities, and find the link to view the Forum (Message and Involve steps).

Realization: The website was created by WP8 and resides at <https://xr4human.eu/>. It features a streamlined vertical design, see figure 1, presenting the mission and goals of the project, relevant news and announcements, representatives of the consortium partners, and prominently features video content produced by WP8 (for more information, please refer to D8.2: Branding, section 3.1). It has proven to be an effective and valuable resource when introducing XR4HUMAN to stakeholders in all contexts.

Figure 1: Main page of project website

2.2 The Forum

Plan: The Forum is to serve as a crucial meeting point between the consortium and stakeholders within the XR4HUMAN project in the form of a curated collection of online chat threads. It enables the consortium to disseminate findings and receive input from stakeholders, facilitating the development of project requirements and deliverables. The goal is to integrate diverse European and cross-sectoral perspectives to advance adherence to recommendations such as the Code of Conduct and Interoperability Guidelines. By addressing the existing 'symmetry of ignorance', the Forum promotes social creativity to achieve project goals, corresponding to steps of empowerment, collaboration, value creation, and innovation. To ensure the project's legacy and sustainable impact, the Forum will be hosted on XR4EUROPE's website for the duration of the project and five years afterward, thus at least until the end of October 2030. A redirection link will remain on the XR4HUMAN website for the same length of time.

Realization: The visual design of the Forum is depicted below in figures 2 and 3. The final design of the platform is largely determined by the Discourse platform, which was selected as the technical platform for the Forum, and which allows slightly more functional variety than aesthetic variety. For this reason, it is not completely aligned with the project's branding.

Figure 2: Main page of the Forum, presenting categories and supporting documents

Figure 3: Example of topic, including chat posts

Renewed communication about the Forum began in February 2024, with virtual event activations of the Forum starting in March 2024. Viewership figures have increased significantly in this time, achieving a recent peak of over 500 views per week, as depicted in figure 3.

Figure 3: Increase in weekly views of discussion topics in the Forum, January 2024 to April 2024

The number of registered users has also increased, but not as quickly as the number of non-registered viewers. Till now, the platform has attracted increasing attention to the discussion topics aligned with WPs' objectives and more general topics; presently 'Best Practices in XR Design', 'Code of Conduct', 'Impact of the Project', 'Interoperability Guidelines', 'Rating System', 'Regulatory Gap Analysis', 'Human Rights', and 'Gen AI and XR' that are presented there, but fewer viewers than desired are sharing their own thoughts and opinions.

Adaptation: The launch of the Forum was delayed by the process of validating and securing the necessary data processing documents. As the Forum neared launch and other WPs were engaged with greater clarity of need and capability, extra care was taken to re-evaluate the nature of user data generation on the platform and to adapt the necessary code of conduct, privacy agreements, and data processing agreements. As many of the tasks that are to engage stakeholders will do so in the second half of the project, it became a challenge to populate the Forum with discussion content for external audiences to view and contribute to. For this reason, LinkedIn Live interviews on related ethics topics were initiated to generate additional visibility around the Forum and generate initial discussion content.

2.3 Working Groups

Plan: A group of stakeholders will be designated to study and provide recommendations on specific questions, aligning with the Involve and Empower steps of the XR4HUMAN project. Coordinated by XR4EUROPE, consortium members will establish working groups (WGs) to develop the Code of Conduct, Interoperability Guidelines, and Rating System. Guidelines will be provided to ensure the quality and autonomy of these groups, harmonizing outputs and fostering innovation from the 'symmetry of ignorance'. Possible topics include ethical frameworks, risks from XR technologies, and interoperability. These WGs will operate throughout the project, supporting a feedback loop between stakeholders and consortium partners, thus contributing to the Create Value step. The formation of WGs will be based on consortium progress and member needs.

Realization: WP leaders, particular OpenARCloud, collaborated to create a list of 93 relevant stakeholders, representing identified and prioritized organizational, service, and expertise characteristics (see Table 1). These criteria were developed to provide a more detailed identification of roles in the XR ecosystem. The list is ready to support the WP tasks that will be engaging stakeholders in the coming months, which are presented in section 3.4 of this report.

Table 1: Descriptive criteria of identified stakeholders

Organisation type	Type of Services	Expertise
Agency / Studio	Assistance	3D Printing
Association / Foundation	Awareness	Artificial intelligence
Cluster	Conception	Augmented Reality / Mixed Reality
Large Enterprise	Decision Making	BIM / SLAM
Public entity	Diagnosis	Captation / Tracking
Research Centre	Discovery / POC	Haptics
SME	Gaming Contents	Holography
Start-up	Historical Memories	IOT/Wearables
University	Maintenance	Machine Learning
	Marketing/Communication	RR Related Tech
	Medical Device	Robotics
	Re-education / Rehabilitation	360 Video
	Remote Monitoring / Alerts	Virtual Humans / Avatars
	Sales/ Retail/ Merchandising	Virtual creation tools
	Teaching/ Therapy/ Training	Virtual Reality
	Virtual Worlds / Social VR	

2.4 Conference and Events

Plan: Participation in conferences and events is crucial for the XR4HUMAN project to engage with current and potential stakeholders, aligning with the Message, Involve, Collaborate, and Empower steps. Opportunities include presenting or speaking on panels on topics like ethics and interoperability, presenting consortium papers, organizing poster sessions and working groups, and networking to expand outreach. By attending such events, XR4HUMAN can establish itself within the community, gaining value in the eyes of stakeholders. The consortium has identified a list of relevant European and worldwide events catering to B2B, research, B2C, and general public audiences, ensuring broad exposure and engagement opportunities.

Realization: Project partners have been very active in attending physical conferences and events organized around relevant topics, as presented in table 2. In total, XR4HUMAN has been represented at

- 13 conferences; including AWE Europe, NordicVR, VRDays' Immersive Tech Week, Research to Realities, Kongsberg Vision Meeting, Tech Ethos, ENRIO Congress on Research Integrity Practice, and the Society for Philosophy and Technology
- 2 industry meetups
- 3 virtual events

Activities at the conferences ranged from research presentations and delivering workshops to speaking on panels and networking. Most conferences targeted a broad mix of industry, innovators, civil society, and research communities, while others focused more specifically on research communities

(Kongsberg Vision Meeting), creators and developers (AWE Europe), or policymakers (Research to Realities).

Table 2: List of conferences and events at which XR4Europe has been represented

Project Partner Involved	Event Name	Type of Event	Date Activity	Target Audience	Description of Activities
Open AR Cloud	AWE Europe	Conference	24.10-25.10.2023	Industry, Developers, Creators, Policy	Panel
HHI, OARC	XR Interaction	Conference	21-Nov-23	Industry, Civil Society, Research	Presentation
USN, XR4Europe, UNIVLEEDS	Nordic VR forum	Conference	15-Nov-23	Industry, Civil Society	Workshop, Keynote
Open AR Cloud	Tech Ethos	Conference	14.11.2023	Policy, Research, Industry	Panel
XR4Europe	AR/VR Industrial Coalition Event	Conference	6-Feb-24	Policy, Industry, Research	Dissemination
NTUA, USN, UiO	2 nd ENRIO Congress on Research Integrity Practice	Conference	07 & 08 Sept 2023	Policy, Research, Users	Dissemination
USN	Kongsberg Vision Meeting	Conference	24-Oct-23	Industry, Research	Presentation, Stand
XR4Europe	Research to Realities	Conference	5-Feb-24	Policy, Industry, Research	Dissemination
USN, UiO	ScAIEM	Conference	1-Dec-23	Industry, Research	Dissemination
USN, UiO	Society for Philosophy and Technology	Conference	7.6.2023-10.6.2023	Industry, Policy, Healthcare, Research	Presentation, Dissemination
USN, UiO, XR4EUROPE	Stereopsia	Conference	18 - 20 Oct 2023	Policy, Industry, Research, Public	Presentation, Workshop
XR4Europe	Foundation Metaverse Europe	Conference	14-Feb-24	Policy, Industry, Research	Dissemination
IFE, Fraunhofer, XR4EUROPE	VRDays' Immersive Tech Week	Conference	28.11.2023-1.12.2023	Policy, Industry, Research, Public	Dissemination
Open AR Cloud, Fraunhofer	XR Interaction Netzwerk	Meet up	21.11.2023	Industry, Research	Dissemination
LEI	XR ERA	Meet up	20-Jul-23	Research, Educators, Industry	Dissemination
XR4Europe	Deep Dive Discussions: XR & AI	Virtual Event	2-Apr-24	Policy, Industry, Research, Public	Interview, Activation
XR4Europe	Deep Dive Discussions: AI & XR Healthcare	Virtual Event	16-Apr-24	Policy, Industry, Research, Public	Interview, Activation
XR4Europe	Deep Dive Discussions: XR & Ethics	Virtual Event	27-Mar-24	Policy, Industry, Research, Public	Interview, Activation

XR4HUMAN's 2023 General Assembly event was paired with a half-day public event that took place on 31 October 2023 at the Fraunhofer Institute for Telecommunications' Showroom Science Tech Space, in Berlin, Germany. The event featured a keynote from invited guest Thomas de Bruyne (see figure 4) and a panel discussion with a member of the project's Advisory Board, Theo Karapiperis, and invited guests Bjorn Hofmann, Etienne Aucouturier, and Muki Kulhan. The public event was attended by more than fifty external persons.

Figure 4: Keynote presentation at XR4HUMAN public event, 31 October 2024

3 Revised Plan for Forthcoming 18 Project Months

This report shows the efforts that have been undertaken by the consortium to develop the number and quality of engaged stakeholders during the first 18 months of XR4HUMAN. The work of engagement will intensify over the remaining 18 months of the project as many tasks that include engagement are set to begin or to produce outputs.

3.1 Forum Development and Activation

The interface design of the Forum is unlikely to change significantly, but the Discourse platform is such that the user experience of the Forum can and will continue to evolve to respond to feedback from engaged stakeholders. One important area being observed is the conversion rate of potential stakeholders to actual registered ones actively participating in Forum discussions. There remains possible friction in this portion of the user experience. XR4Europe will evaluate ways to simplify the process, such as by removing the registration requirement and by reorganizing chat topics for clarity.

Aside from Forum design, virtual events will be utilized more than originally planned to engage stakeholders and to direct them to the Forum. These events are efficient ways to draw attention to specific topics, to engage and recruit stakeholders by presenting them as invited speakers, and to activate and recruit their networks to the Forum.

3.2 Increased Conference and Event Participation

The project partners have been very active in conferences and events, and this is expected to increase in quantity as well as prominence. All research work packages will be delivering many of their objectives in the coming 18 months, which will provide more content for presentations, workshops, and seminars. This content will make it easier for project partners to secure oral presentations to high-profile events, particularly at public-oriented XR festivals and conferences like AWE Europe and VRDays' Immersive Tech Week. XR4Europe's schedule of virtual panels and webinars will also feature WPs' deliverables, and XR4Europe will coordinate with WP8 leaders as dissemination and engagement increasingly overlap during the second half of the project.

Virtual events have been identified as providing important opportunities to engage potential stakeholders that are unlikely or unable to attend physical events. LinkedIn remains the primary platform for these events, but European VR platforms will be used when appropriate for the format of stakeholder engagement, such as for workshops. XR4Europe has secured access to platforms such as Glue (Finland), Raum (Germany), Arthur (Germany), Arrival. Space (Austria), and VRLand (Austria) for this purpose.

3.3 Coordination with Relevant Horizon Projects

The remaining 18 months of the project will leverage the coordination with the OpenVerse project to and XR4Europe's content programming relationship with the Stereopsia EUROPE event to develop deeper engagement with other Horizon Europe projects, particularly the eight projects in which F6S, a London-based social network and online platform for startups, is a partner. XR4Europe is in talks with F6S to coordinate a cross-project program of presentations and networking across multiple days of the 2024 edition of Stereopsia Europe.

The emerging Virtual Worlds Partnership initiative is also expected to present both opportunities and requirements for further coordination between OpenVerse and XR4HUMAN, as both have been identified as CSAs integral to that initiative. XR4Europe has also been identified as one of the XR industry organizations in Europe to support the creation of this new partnership association. The coming 18 months

will respond to the new Virtual Worlds Partnership association in ways to be determined as the structure of the new association becomes clear.

3.4 Schedule of WPs' stakeholder engagements

Many of the stakeholder engagement activities are scheduled to take place over the remaining 18 months, and WP1 will coordinate with task leaders to support and facilitate their stakeholder engagement according to task schedules. The project months in which each task currently plans to engage stakeholders are indicated below and are subject to change.

1. **WP3:**
 - Task 3.4: Governance debate forum (M13-M36): Consultation via the Forum and workshops, involving policymakers and non-profit organizations in M20-M21.
2. **WP4:**
 - Task 4.2: Co-create the project's Interoperability Guideline (M10-M24): Consultation through the Forum and workshops in M19- M20. Asked Open AR Cloud)
3. **WP5:**
 - Task 5.2: Stakeholder consultations (M13-M24): Engagement through the Forum and workshops in M19.
 - Task 5.3: Creation of the XR Code of Conduct (M22-M36): Consultation via the Forum and workshops, in M29-M32.
4. **WP6:**
 - Task 6.4: Evaluation of example use cases (M20-M36): Collaboration with all personas through participant recruitment and evaluation in M25-M30.

This deliverable is awaiting approval from the European Commission